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**FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC, COMMUNICATIVE AND INTERLINGUISTIC
COMPETENCES IN MODERN CONDITIONS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN
TECHNICAL (MARITIME) UNIVERSITY.**

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Abstract.

The article deals with the analysis of the competence approach in teaching foreign languages in higher educational establishments, the formation of linguistic, communicative and interlingual competence of students on the basis of the application of modern educational technologies.

Keywords: competence, linguistic, communicative, intercultural, motivation, communication technologies.

Introduction.

The teaching of foreign languages in higher school at the present stage requires new approaches as the given study material is applied to the students and cadets of the maritime academy where the future specialists work as a part of multinational crews and at times they share the knowledge of English and professional skills.

Literature review and problem statement.

Such training implies not only traditional, actual mastery of all aspects of the language, but also, above all, the formation of a conceptual apparatus of the trainees, enabling cultural and educational orientation and activity. Keeping the main objectives of foreign language training unchanged, the section related to country studies and cultural training should be significantly expanded and strengthened.

The aim and objective of the study.

This task can be realized by using the competence approach in foreign language teaching, which allows transforming a modern student from a passive element of the educational system into an active participant of the educational process, where he/she learns to form his/her world-view, comprehending the experience accumulated by mankind through traditional sources of information and new technologies, and the teacher acts as an adviser, assistant, opponent and consultant. The competence approach not only provides knowledge, but also teaches students how to think independently and acquire knowledge independently.

Thus, the competence-based approach does not prioritise the student's awareness, but rather the ability to solve problems by analogy, which arise in the following situations:

- in the acquisition of modern technology;
- interpersonal relationships, ethical norms, and the assessment of one's own actions;
- in practical life, in the social roles of a citizen, family member, citizen and voter;
- in choosing an occupational specialisation, assessing one's own level of preparedness and orientating oneself on the labour market;
- the need to solve their own problems of self-determination, choice of lifestyle, conflict resolution, etc.

Universalization of the educational system, at the same time, creates a powerful motivation for university students (cadets), as they will see a real opportunity to apply the knowledge received in foreign language classes in a concrete life situation. Undoubtedly, the demand for specialists with knowledge of foreign languages in the labour market will also increase, which will be another additional incentive to this discipline. All this entails changes in the requirements for language proficiency and the definition of new approaches to the selection of content and organisation of material. Thus, the main goal of the competence approach in teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions is to form a comprehensively developed student's personality, his theoretical thinking, language intuition and abilities, mastering the culture of speech communication and behaviour that allows him to be an equal partner of intercultural communication in a foreign language in everyday, cultural and educational-professional spheres.

Materials and methods.

Linguistic competence implies knowing the system of information about the language being studied according to its levels: phonetics, vocabulary, word composition and word formation, morphology, syntax of simple and complex sentences, basic text stylistics. A learner is linguistically competent if he or she has an understanding of the system of the language being studied and is able to use it in practice. The quality of linguistic competence in the language being studied is influenced not only by the degree of proficiency in it, but also by the level of competence in the native language. Acquiring knowledge of the language system is not an end in itself. In the process of forming linguistic competence it is important to develop the student's personality, cognitive culture, logical memory, and to form skills of self-reflection and self-assessment.

Communicative competence implies knowledge of speech, its functions, development of skills in the four main types of speech activities (speaking, listening, reading, writing). Communicative competence of a learner to communicate in a foreign language is the ability to communicate fully in all spheres of human activity, with observance of social norms of speech behaviour. The main skill formed within communicative competence is the ability to create and perceive texts - products of speech activity. It includes knowledge of the basic concepts of speech linguistics - styles, types of speech, structure of description, narration, reasoning, ways of connecting sentences in a text, etc., abilities and skills of text analysis. There are situation components, or speech conditions, that dictate the speaker's choice of words and grammatical means. These are, firstly, the relationship between the interlocutors and their social roles. There is no doubt that the nature of speech communication will be different depending on who we are communicating with, the social status of the speakers, their age, gender, interests, etc. Secondly, the place of communication (e.g. teacher-student communication in class, during a break, in a friendly conversation). A third, very important component of the listening situation is the goal and intention of the speaker. Thus, an order, request or demand will of course be different from a message, information or their emotional evaluation, an expression of gratitude, joy, resentment, etc.

Intercultural competence is an important component of modern training of any university student. This is due to the presence of intercultural aspect of the professional activity of a modern specialist, associated with the interaction of representatives of different cultures, with the performance of productive communicative functions: reaching agreement, overcoming conflicts, the ability to reach consensus through compromise, overcoming communication barriers, which can be the cause of communicative failures, leading to failures in negotiations, inefficient teamwork, social tensions in society. The importance of forming intercultural competence in teaching foreign languages in students is dictated by the radical changes taking place in society as a result of our country's integration into the world educational, informational, economic space, which encourages people to be able to coexist in the common world of life, i.e. to be able and ready to build a constructive dialogue with all subjects of this space, and also by the needs of modern production in specialists ready for cooperation, with communicative.

Results.

The focus of the teaching and learning process in the language education system on the consistent formation of intercultural competence implies the following tasks:

- teaching the norms of intercultural communication in foreign languages;
- socio-cultural development of students (co-education of native language and native culture and foreign languages and cultures of other nations, development of students' abilities and skills to present their country and culture in conditions of foreign-language intercultural communication)
- formation of students' respect for other peoples and cultures, readiness for business cooperation and interaction, joint solution of universal problems.

Discussion of results.

Orientation of the new model to the competent content of education implies formation of communicative competence in the field of foreign language, as well as competences realizing the ability and desire to learn throughout life not only professionally, but also in personal and public life, as well as competences related to life in multicultural society, designed to prevent xenophobia and spreading climate of intolerance. The formation of these competences promotes both the understanding of differences and the readiness to live with people of other cultures, languages and religions.

Conclusion.

Within the competence approach in teaching foreign languages, promising and effective modern technologies of teaching foreign languages are: distance learning through a global network, information and communication technologies modern psychological and pedagogical technologies (learning, role-playing, business games, etc.). Naturally, the technology of communicative learning, i.e. learning through communication, is very promising in modern pedagogy. Communicative pedagogy allows only lessons in the language, not about the language. Communicative teaching also implies consideration of the personal characteristics of the students, because only the personal level allows intensifying the communicative motivation, purposefulness of speaking, etc.

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E-GOVERNMENT AND E-GOVERNANCE: VARIOUS OR MULTIFARIOUS CONCEPTS

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Abstract

E-government and E-governance (as terms and as concepts) are often treated as synonymous and used interchangeably in the academic literature or formal documents. There is no universally accepted definition of both terms / or abstractions. Such conceptual uncertainty has a negative impact on the development of digital democracy. The research objective of this article is to provide a deeper understanding of e-government and e-governance concepts through empirical studies and scatter the existing ambiguity in differences between these two concepts as this variety is not just questions of academic nuance. Based on a comparative analysis of e-government and e-governance definitions and conceptual meanings, this article offers an approach according to which e-government and e-governance represents two closely related and co-existing various concepts.

Keywords: Electronic Government; Electronic Governance; Digital Governance; Digital Democracy; Digital Government.

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous factors have impacted and contributed to the growth and institutionalisation of social phenomenon digital governance and its particular institutional components as followings e-government and e-governance. Generally, it is attributable to the need to respond to the particular pressures or challenges (including increasing budgetary pressures, rising expectations, growing inequality and declining public trust, e-commerce and etc.) facing governments in developed and developing countries (Hannah, 2010). The growth of e-government in developing countries has mainly been driven by external forces, notably the international financial institutions (such as the World Bank and the IMF) (infoDev, 2002; OECD, 2003; Heeks, 2002) and internal issues, primarily the demands for public safety and

security within national borders have necessitated re-thinking on the role of digital facilities in the delivery of services to the public.

Notwithstanding, a unified conceptual or grand vision, regarding e-government and e-governance, has not been achieved yet and the conceptual boundaries of both phenomenon are unclear. Moreover, it is uncertain whether e-government includes both internal and external aspects of public service, such as governance.

Some scholars contend that e-government constitutes only a subset (though a major one) of e-governance - e-governance is a broader concept and includes the use of ICT by government and civil society to promote greater participation of citizens in the governance of political institutions, e.g., use of the Internet by politicians and political parties to elicit views from their constituencies in an efficient manner, or the publicizing of views by civil society organizations which are in conflict with the ruling powers (Howard, 2001; Bannister and Walsh, 2002).

Cook et al. (2002) and Snellen (2006) think that e-government encompasses all aspects of public service delivery and governance. Accordingly, e-governance is a much broader concept, as it encompasses the use of information communication technologies (ICT) in a state's institutional arrangements, decision-making processes, and the implementation of all kinds of changes in relationships between the government and the public; e-government, on the other hand, seems to be essentially a subset of e-governance. Pina eí/i/ (2006) suggests that e-governance includes e-government (UNESCO 2011).

According to Sheridan and Riley (2006), e-governance is a broader concept that deals with the whole spectrum of the relationship and networks within government regarding the usage and application of ICTs whereas e-government is limited to the development of online services).

Other scholars, such as Anttiroik (2007) describes e-government and e-governance as two completely different concepts. E-governance is a broader term comprising a range of relationships and networks in the government, related to the use and application of ICT. E-government is a more restricted area associated with the development of direct (online) services to citizens, paying greater attention to such government services as e-taxes, e-education or e-health. E-governance is a concept that defines the impact of technology on governance practices, the relationship between the government and the public, NGOs and private sector entities. E-governance covers the entire range of government steps develop and administrate, and to ensure successful implementation of e-government services offered to the public. The original idea of e-government has been attributed to the public's need for access to the

government decisions and documents via electronic means, later appeared the need of public electronic services, and finally – a search of opportunities to participate in the decision making process, to consult with the government institutions.

Roy (2007) considers that a distinction must be made between e-governance and e-government, with the former referring to the process of sharing and reorganizing of power across all stakeholders and the citizenry while the latter is more focused on public service delivery. It is possible to perceive the concept of e-government and e-governance very differently depending on their focus (Yildiz, 2007).

Existing conceptual uncertainty is illustrated by Yildiz (2007). According to which some digital interaction tools (G2G, G2C, G2B, G2SC, C2C) is discussed as of e-government or e-governance or e-administration: Government -to-Government (G2G) – belongs to definition of e-administration (example: establishing and using a common data warehouse; Government-to-Citizen (G2C) – belongs to definition of e-government (example: government organization Web Sites, E-mail communication between citizens and government officials); Government-to-Business (G2B) – belongs to definition of e-government, e-commerce, e--collaboration) (example: Posting government bids on the Web, e-procurement, e-partnerships); Government-to-Civil Society Organisations (G2SC) – belongs to definition of e-governance (example: electronic communications and coordination efforts after disaster); Citizen-to-Citizen (C2C) - belongs to definition of e-governance (example: electronic discussion groups on civic issues).

It is clear that considerable confusion exists in explaining e-government and e-governance domains. Follow this, we attempt to resolve such ambiguity and come up with non-overlapping understanding of both phenomenon by reviewing and analyzing existing conceptual framework that provides details and establishes relationships of key variables or similarities.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 E-government: Conceptual Visions

There is not any universally accepted definition or conceptual view of the e-government (Halchin, 2004) however official institutions and academic society offers various ones of e-government such as follows:

- (a) United Nations - “E-government has been employed to mean everything from ‘online government services’” to ‘exchange of information and services electronically with

citizens, businesses, and other arms of government. E-government can thus be defined as the use of ICTs to more effectively and efficiently deliver government services to citizens and businesses. It is the application of ICT in government operations, achieving public ends by digital means. The underlying principle of e-government, supported by an effective e-governance institutional framework, is to improve the internal workings of the public sector by reducing financial costs and transaction times so as to better integrate work flows and processes and enable effective resource utilization across the various public sector agencies aiming for sustainable solutions. Through innovation and e-government, governments around the world can be more efficient, provide better services, respond to the demands of citizens for transparency and accountability, be more inclusive and thus restore the trust of citizens in their governments.”

(b)United Nations (AOEMA report) - “E-government is defined as utilizing the Internet and the world-wide-web for delivering government information and services to citizens.”

(c)World Bank - “E-Government” refers to the use by government agencies of information technologies (such as Wide Area Networks, the Internet, and mobile computing) that have the ability to transform relations with citizens, businesses, and other arms of government. These technologies can serve a variety of different ends: better delivery of government services to citizens, improved interactions with business and industry, citizen empowerment through access to information, or more efficient government management. The resulting benefits can be less corruption, increased transparency, greater convenience, revenue growth, and/or cost reductions.”

(d)EU Parliament - “e-Government refers to efforts by public authorities to use information and communication technologies (ICTs) to improve public services and increase democratic participation. E-Government aims to improve government efficiency through the reduced cost of electronic information management and communications, the reorganization of government agencies and the reduction of administrative silos of information.”

(e)OECD - “The term “e-government” focuses on the use of new information and communication technologies (ICTs) by governments as applied to the full range of government functions. In particular, the networking potential offered by the Internet and related technologies has the potential to transform the structures and operation of government.”

(f) Working Group on E-government in the Developing World - “E-government is the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) to promote more efficient and effective government, facilitate more accessible government services, allow greater public access to information, and make government more accountable to citizens. E-government might involve delivering services via the Internet, telephone, community centers (self-service or facilitated by others), wireless devices or other communications systems.”

(g) United States of America - ...“electronic Government’ means the use by the Government of web-based Internet applications and other information technologies, combined with processes that implement these technologies, to - “(A) enhance the access to and delivery of Government information and services to the public, other agencies, and other Government entities; or “(B) bring about improvements in Government operations that may include effectiveness, efficiency, service quality, or transformation; information and services to the public, other agencies, and other Government entities.”

(h) IGI Global - “This term can be defined as the use of ICTs to more effectively and efficiently deliver government services to citizens and businesses. It is the application of ICT in government operations, achieving public ends by digital means. The use of or application of information technologies (such as Internet and intranet systems) to government activities and processes in order to facilitate the flow of information from government to its citizens, from citizens to government and within government. Refers to the use of new information and communication technologies (ICTs) by governments as applied to the full range of government functions.”

(i) Gartner Group (2000) - ...“the continuous optimization of service delivery, constituency participation, and governance by transforming internal and external relationships through technology, the Internet and new media.”

(j) GBDe definition cited from Bashar, Rezaul and Grout (2011) - “Electronic government (hereafter e-Government) refers to a situation in which administrative, legislative and judicial agencies (including both central and local governments) digitize their internal and external operations and utilize networked systems efficiently to realize better quality in the provision of public services.”

- (k) Key deferences (2017) - “e-Government implies the implementation of information and communication technology like internet, to improve government activities and process, with the aim of increasing efficiency, transparency, and citizen involvement. On the other hand. e-Government may be defined as the integration of information and communication technology, in public administration, i.e. to various government processes, operations, and structures with the purpose of enhancing transparency, efficiency, accountability and citizen participation. It facilitates: Greater level of efficiency and effectiveness in government activities and process. Enhances quality of public services; Simplifies administrative processes; Improves access to information; Increases communication between various government agencies; Strengthen support to public policy; Enables seamless government.”
- (l) Norris and Moon (2005) - “The electronic provision of information and services by governments, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.”
- (m) Kraemer and King (2003) - “The use of information technology within government to achieve more efficient operations, better quality of service, and easy public access to government information and services.”
- (n) Brown (2005) - “The entire range of government roles and activities, shaped by and making use of information and communications technologies.”
- (o) Cook, Lavigne, Pagano, Dawes and Pardo (2002) - “The uses of information technology to support operations, engage citizens, and provide government services.”
- (p) Fang (2002) - ...”is defined e-government as a way for governments to use the most innovative information and communication technologies, particularly web-based Internet applications, to provide citizens and businesses with more convenient access to government information and services, to improve the quality of the services and to provide greater opportunities to participate in democratic institutions and processes.”
- (q) Fraga (2002) - ...”e-government involves the use of ICTs to support government operations and provide government services.”
- (r) Leitner (2003) - ...”e-government goes even further and aims to fundamentally transform the production processes in which public services are generated and delivered, thereby transforming the entire range of relationships of public bodies with citizens, businesses and other governments.”

E-government is also perceived differently in connection with its theoretical background. According to Garson (1999), there are four theoretical frameworks within which e-government is conceptualised. The first framework involves the potential of IT in decentralization and democratization. The second normative/ dystopian framework underlines the limitations and contradictions of technology. Third, the sociotechnical systems approach emphasizes the continuous and two-way interaction of the technology and the organizational–institutional environment. The fourth framework places e-government within theories of global integration.

Examination of official documents, analytical or scientific literature shows that “e-government” continues to evolve, depending on the context. As Homburg (2008) outlines that e-government is hence multifaceted and has been implemented in a variety of forms and shapes, further complicating the process of trying to determine a single, universal meaning.

E-government, characterised as a multifaced concept, has a different meaning to different constituents (Gauld and Goldfinch, 2006): for politicians e-government plays role an engine for reform and to meet the aspirations of new public management; for the general public, e-government is viewed as a source of greater information and influence on government; for the bureaucrats, e-government is viewed as a managerial tool to improve their service delivery.

E-government has been discussed in different aspects: in the context of technology (Zhiyuan, 2002); from a service delivery perspective (Norris and Moon 2005); from a citizen-centric perspective (Roy, 2007); from a functional perspective (Selfert and Petersen, 2002); from a social fabric perspective (Brown, 2005); and from a radical change perspective (Kraemer and King 2008).

2.2 E-governance: Conceptual Visions

Just as there are many conceptual views of governance, there are many conceptual approaches of e-governance (Godse and Garg, 2011). Although they do not always run inline, generally e-governance refers to the use of information and communication technologies to transform and support the processes and structures of a governance system. In order to cover the variety of uses and the nuances sufficiently, several definitions / meanings of e-governance.

(a) Council of Europe - “E-governance is about the use of information technology to raise the quality of the services governments deliver to citizens and businesses. It is

hoped that it will also reinforce the connection between public officials and communities thereby leading to a stronger, more accountable and inclusive democracy.”

(b)UNESCO - “E-governance is the public sector’s use of information and communication technologies with the aim of improving information and service delivery, encouraging citizen participation in the decision-making process and making government more accountable, transparent and effective. E-governance involves new styles of leadership, new ways of debating and deciding policy and investment, new ways of accessing education, new ways of listening to citizens and new ways of organizing and delivering information and services. E-governance is generally considered as a wider concept than e-government, since it can bring about a change in the way citizens relate to governments and to each other. E-governance can bring forth new concepts of citizenship, both in terms of citizen needs and responsibilities. Its objective is to engage, enable and empower the citizen.”

(c)ÖKTEM, DEMİRHAN (2004) - “Electronic governance (e-governance) applications are related to both the usage of technology and citizen participation in politics. “Electronic” indicates the technological capacities of our age and “governance” is a new perspective in government paradigm. Innovations in both technology and perspective create new understandings for governing such as “governing with people.”

(d)Bedi, Singh and Srivastava (2001), Holmes (2001), Okot-Uma (2000) - ...“meaning ‘electronic governance’ is using information and communication technologies (ICTs) at various levels of the government and the public sector and beyond, for the purpose of enhancing Governance.”

(e)Keohane and Nye (2000) - “Governance implies the processes and institutions, both formal and informal, that guide and restrain the collective activities of a group. Government is the subset that acts with authority and creates formal obligations. Governance need not necessarily be conducted exclusively by governments. Private firms, associations of firms, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), and associations of NGOs all engage in it, often in association with governmental bodies, to create governance; sometimes without governmental authority.”

- (f) Clift (2003) - "E-democracy builds on e-governance and focuses on the actions and innovations enabled by ICTs combined with higher levels of democratic motivation and intent."
- (g) Backus (2001) - "E-governance is defined as the, "application of electronic means in (1) the interaction between government and citizens and government and businesses, as well as (2) in internal government operations to simplify and improve democratic, government and business aspects of Governance."
- (h) IGI Global - "Electronic Governance is the application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) for delivering government services through integration of various stand-alone systems between Government-to-Citizens (G2C), Government-to-Business (G2B), and Government-to-Government (G2G) services. It is often linked with back office processes and interactions within the entire government framework. Through e-Governance, the government services are made available to the citizens in a convenient, efficient, and transparent manner."
- (i) Oakley (2002) - "A technology mediated service that facilitates a transformation in the relationship between government and citizen."
- (j) Riley (2001) cited by Saxena (2003) - The commitment to utilize appropriate technology for a variety of ends including greater democracy and fair and efficient services.
- (k) Palvia and Sharma (2007) - "Propose a framework for differentiating between e-government and e-governance. In their model, e-governance is concerned with internally focused use of ICT to manage organizational resources and administer policies and procedures; e-government is outward and citizen directed."
- (l) Sheridan and Riley (2010) - "... deals with the whole spectrum of the relationship and networks within government regarding the usage and application of ICTs."
- (m) Chen and Hsish (2009) - "The use of ICT to improve the quality of services and governance (cf UNESCO)."
- (n) Marche and McNiven (2003) - "... " a technology-mediated relationship between citizens and their governments from the perspective of potential electronic deliberation over civic communication, over policy evolution and in democratic expressions of citizen."

- (o) Dawes (2008) and Potnis (2009) - "ICTs provide interactive communication channels, which are important in the transformation of the current governing process to a governing process that is open to the collaboration and deliberation of different actors in the processes of service provision and information delivery."
- (p) Pina et al., (2007), Sandoval-Almazan and Gil-Garcia (2012) - "E-governance refers to the use of ICTs to reach the aims related to governance. Governance can be explained in terms of its main components. These components are participation, transparency and accountability, information and service delivery, and communication and interaction in governing processes."
- (q) Lean, Zailani, Ramayah, and Fernando (2009), Yildiz (2007) - "E-governance is related to the use of information and communication technologies in policymaking, legitimating, auditing, counting of government application, providing transparency and accountability of governments, and service delivery."
- (r) OECD (2001) - ... "means "preparing for greater and faster interactions with citizens and ensure better knowledge management."
- (s) Prabha (2004) - "A form of e-business in governance comprising of process and structures involved in deliverance of electronic service to the public, viz. citizens."
- (t) Kettl (2002) - "The impact [from e-government interactions] on government, public service and citizens throughout the political process, policy development, program design and service delivery."
- (u) Oakley (2002) - "A technology mediated service that facilitates a transformation in the relationship between government and citizen."
- (v) Gordon (2002), Signore et al., (2005) - ... "defines e-government as the use of ICT to improve the process of government. In a narrow sense it is sometimes defined as citizen's services, re-engineering with technology, or procurement over Internet."
- (w) Spremić et al. (2009) - ... "e-government denotes the use of information technologies
- (x) and the Internet for better delivery government services to citizens. It denotes also a more efficient management and improvement of interactions between government and citizens."
- (y) Marthandan and Tang (2010) - ... "interactions between economic, political and social actors. Indeed e-government allows businesses to transact with each other more efficiently (B2B) and brings customers closer to businesses (B2C). Also, e-

government enable links between government and citizens (G2C), government and businesses enterprises (G2B) and interagency relationships (G2G).”

(z) Signore et al. (2005) - “E-governance is a concept larger than the concept of e-government since it can bring about a change in the way how citizens relate to government and to each other.”

(aa) Key differences (2017) - “e-Governance means governing or administering a country/state or organization, with the help of information and communication technology.

(bb) Electronic governance, shortly known as e-governance refers to the utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) for providing government services, disseminating information, communication activities, and incorporation of miscellaneous stand alone system and services between different models, processes and interaction within the overall structure. E-governance is a tool, that makes available various government services to citizens in a convenient way, such as: Better provision of government services; Improved interaction with different groups; Citizen empowerment through access to information; Efficient government management.”

(cc) Margolis and Moreno-Riano (2010) - ...”e-governance is focused on the democratic processes.”

(dd) Budd and Harris (2009), UNESCO (2005) 0 "e-governance is the use of information and communication technologies in public administration in order to improve the information and public service, encouraging the citizens' participation in the decision-making processes and making the government more accountable, transparent and effective."

Depending on the particular conditions and governance requirements or activities, Halachmi (2007) suggests five important models of e-governance: (i) The Broadcasting Model of dissemination of useful governance information to have informed citizenry; (ii) The Critical Flow Model of routing information of critical value to the targeted audience; (iii) The Comparative Analysis Model of assimilation of best practices in the field of governance for developing countries to empower their people; (IV) The E-Advocacy/Mobilisation and Lobbying Model of adding the opinions of virtual communities so that the global civil society can have an impact on global decision-making processes; (v) The Interactive-Service Model of individuals' direct participation in governance processes to

bring in greater objectivity and transparency in decision-making processes.

2.3 E-government and E-governance Terms Components

The “E” part of both e-government and e-governance stands for the electronic platform or infrastructure that enables and supports the networking of public policy development and deployment (Sheridan and Riley, 2006).

Government is an institutional superstructure that society uses to translate politics into policies and legislation. Governments are specialised institutions that contribute to governance. Governments are bureaucratically organized and constitutionally legitimated. They serve as both the highest forum for policy making within their jurisdictions, and as the final court of appeal within their jurisdictions for dissenters to those policies. Most of the work of governments consists of actually implementing policies through service delivering programs. Individuals and groups assess governmental performance in terms of their own perception. Governments often face the need to rationalize discrepancies amongst people's desires to achieve their own ends (Godse and Garg, 2011).

Governance is the outcome of the interaction of government, the public service, and citizens throughout the political process, policy development, program design, and service delivery. The institution of government involves a narrower range of considerations than the wider functions of governance. Governance is distinct from government as it concerns longer-term processes rather than immediate decisions. Governance is a set of continuous processes that usually evolve slowly with use unlike government. The governance focuses on processes instead of decisions. Governance takes the larger view of social objectives, so it involves the coordination of efforts rather than the implementation of specific programs. This is the systemic perspective as opposed to a focus on the individual practice, or player, or process. The "bottom line" for governance is outcomes rather than the outputs of government (Godse and Garg, 2011).

3. CONCLUSION

A comparative analysis of e-government and e-governance reveals that discussed concepts have to be considered as two distinct abstractions (Sheridan and Riley, 2010):

(a) E-government is an institutional approach to jurisdictional political operations and a narrower discipline dealing with the development of online services to the citizen, more than any particular government service – such as e-tax, e-transportation or e-health, such as not for profits organizations, NGOs or private sector corporate entities.

(b) E-governance is a procedural approach to co-operative administrative relations, i.e. the encompassing of basic and standard procedures within the confines of public administration. It is the latter that acts as the lynchpin that will ensure success of the delivery of e-services. E-governance is a broader topic that deals with the whole spectrum of the relationship and networks within government regarding the usage and application of ICTs. E-governance is a wider concept that defines and assesses the impacts technologies are having on the practice and administration of governments and the relationships between public servants and the wider society, such as dealings with the elected bodies or outside groups. E-governance encompasses a series of necessary steps for government agencies to develop and administer to ensure successful implementation of e-government services to the public at large. The differences between these two important constructs are explored further in this essay.

Based on the results of the study conceptual frameworks of e-government and e-governance are based on following main strategic pillars: e-government is a system whereas e-governance is a functionality, e-government is a one-way communication protocol. On the contrary, e-governance is a two-way communication protocol (Kafle, 2018).

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**PECULIARITIES OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES
FORMATION IN THE SPECIALTY OF BIOLOGY AT HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF POLYLINGUAL EDUCATION**

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Abstract

Background information: The transition of secondary schools in Kazakhstan to the updated content of education, one of the features in which is the teaching of Biology as a subject in English, determines the relevance of training teachers who are competent in the aspect of multilingual education. However, in the real practice of teaching students on the specialty "Biology", the formation of professional competencies of future teachers is insufficiently integrated with the tasks of multilingual education, which is carried out mainly at the empirical level without sufficient scientific and methodological support.

The problems of the competence-based approach in training of future teachers were considered in the works of M.Zh.Dzhadrina, D.M.Kazakhbayeva, Sh.Sh.Karbayeva, K.K. Zhumagulova, A.K.Mynbayeva. The problems of the future teacher multilingual competences formation were also reviewed by B.A. Zhetpisbayeva, N.Sh. Almetov, A.N. Zhorabekova in their publications. However, the issues of students' multilingual competences formation in speciality "Biology" remains little researched.

Materials and methods: at various stages of research, we used methods of pedagogical observation, questioning of students and teachers, study and analysis of mass and advanced university experience in multilingual education of students, pedagogical experiment, method of expert assessment, methods of mathematical statistics.

Results: the analysis of the practice of multilingual students' teaching in the specialty "Biology" at higher educational institutions has shown that there are many factors that reduce its effectiveness. These factors include: lack of system integration in competence-based and

multilingual approaches in teaching students of the specialty “Biology”; insufficient adaptation level of existing approaches and methods of multilingual education to the conditions of teaching Biology to Biology students; insufficient teaching orientation of Biology students to the activities of a Biology teacher working in multilingual programs.

Conclusions: the effectiveness of the process of students’ professional competencies forming in the specialty “Biology” in conditions of multilingual education is ensured by the integration of competence-based and multilingual approaches in the following areas: development of linguistic and communicative competencies of students at all stages of pedagogical education at the university; application of the subject-language integrated learning (CLIL) methodology in teaching Biology in English; introduction of communicative methods in teaching a foreign language.

Key words: multilingual education, competence, professional competence, communicative competence, content and language integrated learning (CLIL), future Biology teacher.

Introduction

The competence-based approach in defining the goal and content of education is not a new concept. In 1980s-1990s didactic schools of famous scientists-educators M.N.Skatkin [1], I. Ya. Lerner [2] and V.V.Krayevsky [3] recommended ideas close to competence in education, creative activity of students and their emotionally valued relationships. This idea is the basis of the competence-based approach in education, oriented for the results.

Meanwhile, in the conceptual documents and in the real educational practice of the former Soviet Union countries for many decades there was a conservative and cognitive approach to the formation and assessment of learning outcomes, i.e. orientation of the teaching and education process to knowledge, skills and abilities.

The approval of the competence-based approach as a basic methodological guideline for the development of educational programs and the organization of the educational process is associated with the acquisition of state independence by Kazakhstan, the desire for the Kazakh education system to enter the world educational space. Conceptual documents for the development of education and science in the Republic of Kazakhstan, adopted and implemented in recent years, declare the competence approach as a principle of goal setting, design, organization and assessment of the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in organizations of general, post-secondary, higher and postgraduate professional education [4; 5; 6].

The competence-based approach in education consists of a set of general principles in defining the goal of education, selecting the content of education, organizing the educational process and evaluating the results [7]. Practical activity of students in the process of implementing the competence-based approach in education is one of the main components of didactic methods [5, 6]. Thus, the leading idea of modern higher professional education is to harmonize the component of the education effectiveness with the planned result of personality development. In the real practice of higher educational institutions, the competence-based approach is gaining more and more actual importance.

Methodological and theoretical aspects of the competence-based approach in education are highlighted in the works of A. Khutorskaya [7], E.A.Shishov [8], I.A. Zimnyaya [9].

The issues of professional competence formation on the basis of a person-centred approach were the subjects of monographic research by A.K.Mynbaeva [10], Sh.T.Taubayeva and S.N. Laktionova [11] who investigated the problems of professional competencies formation of future teachers in the context of pedagogical innovation problems.

Approaches to solving modern problems of organizing educational process in higher educational institutions in conditions of credit technology based on a competence-based approach to determining the quality of specialists training have been analyzed and summarized in the monograph by A.K.Narkoziev [12].

In the aspect of our research the interest represents the monograph of E.Sh. Kozybaev, V.P. Bondarenko and E.V.Ponomarenko [13], where they developed the theoretical foundations of the national qualifications system formation based on the competence-based approach.

In the work of M.N.Sarybekov [14], there given qualification characteristic of a teacher and it is considered as the basis for the formation of professional competencies of a future teacher in a higher pedagogical educational institution.

There are many complementary interrelated definitions of the professional competence concept in the pedagogical literature. Thus, V.M.Shepel [15] interprets the concept of competence as knowledge, qualification, experience, theoretical and practical preparation for using the knowledge gained.

E.F.Zeer [16] defines competence as a set of professional knowledge and skills, as well as methods and ways of performing professional activities.

The English scientist N. Norris rightly notes, who proposes to distinguish between the concepts of expertise and competence. The author proposes to consider expertise as a personal category, and competence as a unit of the curriculum [17].

Multilingual education as an important and most promising trend in the development of higher professional education in the era of globalization is closely intertwined with another, no less relevant context - a competence-based approach to education, which has received broad rights in the practice of higher education in the Republic of Kazakhstan, on its way to joining the Bologna process.

In the context of globalization, the expansion of the educational field of teaching in English, multilingual education seems to be very relevant. Multilingual education is understood not only the use of two or more languages as a means of teaching and learning, but also gaining an education that creates conditions and opportunities for students to use their native languages.

There is of great interest the experience of multilingual learning described in the article [Shiby Stephens and Bernard John Moxham], which describes an approach to multilingual learning, which describes experiences related to the development of academic literacy skills among students for whom English is a second or additional language. The author, in particular, writes: “The UCT language policy obliges the university to clearly teach all students about literacy and language skills across disciplines, which is challenging because UCT attracts students with such diverse language and school backgrounds. But LDG considers the mother tongue / s3 as an important resource for the development of a second language”.

The author further comments that “empowering our students to use their native languages can act as a tool for learning and providing access to the discourses of their disciplines (Baker 1993). This not only gives epistemological access, but students feel more welcome and confident when they hear and see their languages in university halls and classrooms. Therefore, Language Development staff have introduced various innovations in this area, such as encouraging and supporting students to use their native languages as a tool for developing ideas and concepts (Kapp 1998) by providing native language teaching materials and educating teachers to use multilingualism as a resource ”[18].

The authors put forward the following conceptual provisions for multilingual education: “Without discussing concepts in the main language, alternative concepts of some students may go unnoticed. Teachers may not be aware that writing in English and multiple

choice questions hide misconceptions as learners resort to rote learning because they do not fully understand English texts and memorization is seen as the only way to gain information. If we want to provide our second language students with access to new concepts, they need to be provided with opportunities to explore ideas and concepts in both English and their main languages” [18].

Note that in the experience of multilingual education in higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan, for students who consider English as an additional language (after the state Kazakh and official Russian languages), the issue of building multilingual education models using native languages is also relevant. There is an opinion among Kazakhstani practitioners about the advisability of models for full or partial immersion in target languages in multilingual education. However, our long-term observations show that supporting and encouraging the use of the mother tongue in multilingual education in higher education only goes to the benefit of obtaining academic knowledge in the target (English) language.

Moragh Isobel Jane Paxton's study provides with compelling examples concerning the effectiveness of multilingual teaching in developing spatial and verbal intelligence in medical students in teaching anatomy.

The authors are convinced that “medical students represent a useful group of university students to assess the importance of multilingualism in the development of spatial and verbal intelligence. They are often considered academically gifted and have a complex curriculum and learning regime (there is a significant body of knowledge to be acquired and many precise skills to be acquired)” [19].

The authors collected and analyzed voluminous material regarding the assumption that “medical students with multilingualism have higher spatial and verbal intelligence”, “if medical students speaking different languages have higher spatial and verbal intelligence, they cope better with examinations in anatomy”. The authors tested the hypotheses using questionnaires sent out to medical students at the University of Cardiff, whose exam results were available anonymously and in accordance with the agreed guidelines of the ethics committee of the University of Cardiff”[19].

The authors describe the following research methodology: “Two sets of data were available for analysis regarding the performance of the surveyed students. First, the students took formative anatomy tests, which consisted primarily of questions requiring the identification of anatomical structures from human cadaver samples. Therefore, these questions required spatial intelligence skills. Second, students passed final exams, which

consisted of multiple-choice questions, more appropriate for those requiring verbal intelligence skills. Data were placed in Excel spreadsheets and analyzed using Anderson-Darling normality tests, Mann-Whitney U tests, Cronbach and Kruskal-Wallis alpha tests”[19].

The results of the statistical processing of the data allowed the authors to draw the following scientifically sound conclusions, that is, “Students who speak the same language (speak only English) demonstrate less verbal and spatial intelligence than multilingual groups. At the same time, “students who are fluent in English and other non-European languages perform better on both verbal and spatial intelligence tests” [19].

It is necessary to pay attention to another important point identified by the authors of this study. Multilingualism develops the spatial and verbal intelligence of medical students, at the same time contributing to the development of the professionally important qualities of the future specialist. Here is what the authors write about this: “Anatomical terms are derived from classical languages such as Greek and Latin, and a good understanding of these languages will help with knowledge recall and therefore with exam results. This advantage seems to have disappeared when it comes to interpreting questions of spatial and verbal intelligence. Understanding these languages could not affect the brain in the same way as language acquisition. Consequently, benefits were not evident when addressing spatial and verbal intelligence issues in the questionnaire. Our results show that students who are fluent in English and other non-European languages perform better with both spatial and oral intelligence”[19].

In Kazakhstan, there is a great scientific interest to the problems of multilingual competencies formation in the aspect of multilingual education associated with two factors:

- with the implementation of trilingual education programs (Kazakh, Russian, English) in the system of higher professional education, with the aim of increasing the competitiveness of the future specialist in the labor market, academic and professional mobility, raising the rating of Kazakhstani universities at the international level;

- with the introduction of trilingual education in organizations of general secondary education in connection with the implementation of the updated content of education, the relevance of the search for scientifically grounded solutions to the problems of multilingual and multicultural education in the school where the graduates of the pedagogical university will work.

The fundamental aspects of professional competencies formation of a future teacher in the context of multilingual education in a higher educational institution are considered in the dissertation work of B.A.Zhetpisbayeva [20]. In the formation of multilingual education, the author focuses more on the linguistic training of the future teacher.

In her dissertation work A.N. Zhorabekova [21] studies the process of forming the professional competencies of a future teacher on the basis of a multilingual approach.

In the works of N.Sh.Almetov there were considered various aspects of the formation of multilingual competences of a future teacher: pedagogical design of the professional readiness of a future teacher for the implementation of multilingual programs; the continuity of the formation process and development of professional competencies of a teacher at the university and in real school practice; development of students' creative thinking in a multilingual educational environment [22; 23].

The problems of a competence-based approach to the educational process, in particular, in the process of natural science education at school and university were the subject of research by many Kazakhstani scientists.

Thus, M.Zh.Dzhadrina [24], D.M. Kazakhbayeva [25] conducted research on the structural and substantive aspects of natural science education at school based on the implementation of the competence model.

Meanwhile, despite positive trends in the introduction of trilingual education in the practice of the educational process of training future teachers, there are many aspects of preparing students of pedagogical higher educational institutions for multilingual education which remain insufficiently studied. In particular, the analysis of literature and mass university practice of preparing students for multilingual education in Kazakhstan on the basis of a competency-based approach allows us to draw the following conclusions:

- despite the fact that pedagogical higher educational institutions have accumulated a certain positive experience in developing educational programs, organizing the educational process and monitoring its results on the basis of a competency-based approach, the multilingual approach is not sufficiently represented in them;

- the problems of training future teachers on the basis of integration of the competence-based and multilingual approach are in most cases solved at the empirical level, without sufficient scientific and scientific-methodological support, which is due to insufficient research of this problem in pedagogical science;

- the formation of professional competencies of the future teacher in teaching natural scientific disciplines, in particular, Biology in conditions of multilingual education in the specific terms of organizations of general secondary education of the Republic of Kazakhstan remains low researched in pedagogical science.

Higher educational institutions of Kazakhstan practise training of specialists who are professionally ready to teach natural science subjects in a foreign (English) language. However, in the practice of universities, the lack of specialists who are sufficiently fluent in English and the program content in English makes it difficult to promote the goals and objectives of multilingual education. There are also classes in the subjects of natural and mathematical cycle at schools where classes are often conducted by subject teachers who independently study English, or just by English language teachers.

The first President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. Nazarbayev, being the initiator of trilingual education, has repeatedly noted that young people should be equally fluent in Kazakh, Russian and English [26]. Today's student is tomorrow's teacher of a new formation, who should be able to apply the language of world science and education in their professional activities, on a par with the Kazakh and Russian languages.

If until now, students studied in two languages (Kazakh and Russian), from recent years teaching in English has been introduced, and a system of teaching in three languages is being formed.

In this regard, it is important to pay attention to the fact that the main source of trilingualism is the secondary school, for which universities prepare future teachers.

Thus, the problem of the students' professional competencies formation in the specialty "Biology" in higher educational institutions, focused on the tasks of multilingual education, is an urgent scientific problem of practical importance.

The purpose of this article is a theoretical substantiation of students' professional competence formation in the specialty "Biology" in conditions of multilingual education and field-experimental demonstration of the proposed approaches to its methodological support.

RESEARCH METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

In the research of the state and process of students' professional competences formation of the specialty "Biology" of higher educational institutions, we used complex of scientific and pedagogical methods and diagnostic techniques: theoretical analysis of scientific, scientific and methodological literature on the research problem; the study and analysis of the mass and advanced university experience in multilingual education of students; open and closed

questionnaires, interview, control, pedagogical experiment (ascertaining, formative), analysis and differentiation, self-control, expert assessment, mathematical and statistical data processing.

The research methodology is based on:

- modern theories and concepts, revealing the essence of the concepts of “expertise” and “competence”, “multilingual education”;
- theories and concepts of multilingual and multicultural education;
- modern theories and concepts of natural science education;
- competence-based approach to training students of the specialty “Biology”;
- multilingual approach to training of future Biology teachers in higher educational institutions.

Discussions:

We will use content and language integrated learning (CLIL) as the basis for the formation of professional competencies of students on the specialty “Biology” at higher educational institutions in the context of multilingual education.

Ofelia García and Angela M.Y. Lin prove that “the idea of using the principle of content and language integrated learning arose as a result of the increased requirements for the level of foreign language proficiency with a limited time allotted for its study. This approach allows teaching in two subjects at the same time, although the main attention can be paid either to the language or to a non-linguistic subject”[27, p.385].

We are in solidarity with the authors that “the integrated teaching method as a whole, like all didactics, is currently going through a difficult period. The goals of general secondary education have changed, new curricula are being developed, new approaches to the integrated teaching of subjects. And updating the content of education requires the use of non-traditional methods and forms of organizing training, including integrated lessons in various subjects. That is why new ones appear. Educational technologies and one of such technologies is content and language integrated learning called CLIL”[27].

The CLIL methodology considers the study of a target (foreign language) as a tool for studying other subjects. It is especially relevant for teaching Biology at school or at a university, even if the student or student does not have a sufficient level of knowledge of a second (for example, English) language.

The CLIL methodology is undeniably effective for multilingual teaching of students, the formation of their multilingual competencies, as evidenced by numerous research papers

in recent years. However, it is still at the stage of improvement. Thus, Elisa Caruso in “Translanguaging in higher education”: Using several languages for the analysis of academic content in teaching and learning process “calls into question the existence and use of language practices in higher education”. According to the authors’ opinions, “on the one hand, the growth of mobility in higher education leads to the presence of different individual repertoires in the classroom, and on the other hand, the use of scientific texts, usually published in English, is becoming more common. These two factors force the choice of language on professors. In some cases, they may use a single lingua franca, most often English, or in other cases they may undermine the hegemonic role of the English language by using what Garcia calls a translator” [28].

From this point of view, the authors analyze the case study for the course “Language and Communication Policy”. The lecturer of this course allowed students to use their linguistic repertoire using several languages in the classroom to achieve a collective understanding of the content, which was in most cases in English. In this way, they have achieved what (García, Ofelia & Li Wei. 2014. *Translanguaging: Language, Bilingualism and Education*. Hounds. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan) is defined as “collaborative knowledge construction” in a “collaborative classroom learning environment”. The authors also emphasize that “the professor asked the students to take a structured multilingual final exam in three languages to stimulate and develop their multilingual skills” [29].

In the Kazakhstani practice of general secondary education, the CLIL methodology has successfully proven at Nazarbayev Intellectual Schools. The country's pedagogical universities began to switch to teaching some disciplines in English. Although there have been some successful attempts by practicing teachers to teach basic and elective university courses in English, such efforts are not scientifically supported. The methodology of using CLIL technology in the training of future Biology teachers has not yet been subjected to scientific comprehension and scientific and methodological interpretation. We have made an attempt to theoretically substantiate and experimentally test the process of forming professional competencies of future Biology teachers based on the methodology of content and language integrated learning.

To diagnose main characteristics of students’ professional competence formation in the specialty “Biology” at higher educational institutions in conditions of multilingual education, we used the following criteria:

- 1) the level of proficiency in the target (English) language;

- 2) the level of proficiency in the subject content (Biology) in English;
- 3) the level of proficiency in the methods of teaching Biology in English;
- 4) the level of students' communicative competencies in the target (English) language.

Each criterion was expressed in the respective indicators (Table 1).

Table 1 - Criteria and indicators of the of students' multilingual professional competencies formation in the specialty "Biology"

Criteria	Indicators
proficiency in the target (English) language	development of listening, speaking, reading, writing skills
proficiency in subject content (Biology) in English	level of subject knowledge required for high-quality teaching of Biology at school
proficiency in teaching Biology in English	knowledge of modern didactic foundations of teaching the subject "Biology" at school; ability to apply technology of content and language integrated learning (CLIL)
development of students' communicative competencies in the target (English) language;	proficiency in the communicative methodology of teaching languages; the use of communicative methods of teaching languages in teaching Biology.

In accordance with the criteria defined above and taking into account the regulations on the presence of four possible levels of activity of V.P. Bepalko, we have identified four possible levels of students' multilingual professional competencies formation -future Biology teachers (Table 2).

Table 2 - Characteristics of the level students' multilingual professional competencies formation on the specialty "Biology"

Level of multilingual professional competencies formation	Characteristics of levels
I - low level	<p>Diagnostic features are poorly expressed. A student has low developed listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. Subject knowledge in Biology in English is formed at the level of terminology knowledge.</p> <p>The student cannot understand and retell Biology texts, express his/her opinion, apply knowledge to complete subject tasks in English.</p> <p>The student has a vague idea of the modern didactic foundations of teaching the subject "Biology" at school. He/she does not understand the role and significance of CLIL. He/she doesn't know the principles of CLIL and its methodological tools. He/she cannot apply CLIL technology to planning and delivering a Biology lesson at school. He/she does not understand the essence and approaches of the communicative method of teaching languages and is unable to use it in teaching Biology.</p>
II – satisfactory level	<p>The diagnostic features are expressed satisfactorily. The student has generally expressed skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing. However, they are insufficient for full inclusion in a foreign language educational environment. The subject knowledge in Biology in English is formed at the level of understanding and retelling small texts on Biology, expressing one's own judgments, applying knowledge to complete subject tasks in English with the help of a teacher. The student has a little understanding of the modern didactic foundations of</p>

	<p>teaching the subject “Biology” at school. He/she knows and understands the role and importance of content and language integrated learning (CLIL). He/she can list CLIL principles and some of its methodological tools. Occasionally knows how to apply the technology of content and language integrated learning (CLIL) in planning and conducting a Biology lesson at school. He/she knows and understands the essence and approaches of the communicative method of teaching languages. However, he can carry out tasks on the use of communicative methods in teaching Biology with the support of a teacher.</p>
<p>III - sufficient level</p>	<p>Diagnostic features are sufficiently expressed. The student has sufficiently expressed skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing. They are sufficient for full inclusion in a foreign language educational environment.</p> <p>The subject knowledge in Biology in English is formed at the level of application and analysis of Biology texts, expressing one’s own opinions, applying knowledge to perform subject tasks in English with a little help from a teacher. The student has a clear understanding of the modern didactic foundations of teaching the subject “Biology” at school. He/she knows and understands well the role and importance of content and language integrated learning (CLIL). He/she can partially describe the principles of CLIL and some of its methodological tools. He/she is able to use the technology of subject-language integrated learning (CLIL) in planning and conducting a Biology lesson at school in standard situations and partly in non-standard conditions. He/she clearly understands the essence and approaches of the communicative method of teaching languages. He/she can carry out tasks on the use of communicative methods in teaching Biology independently, with a little support from the teacher. However, when completing assignments for teaching Biology in English, he/she</p>

	does not show creativity and complete independence.
IV - high level	Diagnostic features are vividly expressed. The student has clearly expressed listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. He/she is ready for full inclusion in a foreign language educational environment. The subject knowledge in Biology in English is formed at the level of analysis and critical assessment of Biology texts, independent expression of one's own judgments, application of knowledge to complete subject tasks in English without the help of a teacher. The student has a clear understanding of the modern didactic foundations of teaching the subject "Biology" at school. He/she has a clear understanding of the CLIL toolkits. He/she can fully characterize the principles of CLIL and some of its methodological tools. He/she is able to use the technology of content and language integrated learning (CLIL) in planning and conducting a Biology lesson at school in standard situations and partly in non-standard conditions. He/she clearly understands the essence and approaches of the communicative method of teaching languages. He/she can complete tasks on the use of communicative methods in teaching Biology quite independently. When completing assignments for teaching Biology in English, he/she demonstrates creativity and complete independence.

In order to assess the levels of students' multilingual competencies formation and ensure their reliability, the method of expert assessments was used with the participation of experienced teachers of English and Biology of the university. After the expert assessment, interviews were held with students to clarify the assessments of the level of formation of their multilingual competencies. At the same time, no significant difference was found in the assessments of experts and the self-assessment of students based on the results of the interview.

As a material for experimental verification there was used the methodology for the development of multilingual competencies of students at the specialty “Biology”, which was based on the following pedagogical conditions:

- differentiation of students by levels of the target (English) language knowledge proficiency and individualization of the development of program material in Biology courses, the development of linguistic and professional language competencies;
- the use of a system of psychological and pedagogical measures to motivate students to study Biology (university biological courses) in English;
- creation of a foreign language information and educational development environment;
- application of the methodology of the content and language integrated learning (CLIL) in teaching Biology in English;
- the use of communicative methods in teaching languages.

We proceeded from the fact that the use of this system of psychological and pedagogical conditions in the complex ensures the development of multilingual professional competencies of Biology students in pedagogical faculties.

Experimental work to test the effectiveness of the developed pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional competencies of a multilingual student - a future teacher was carried out on the basis of the Abai Kazakh Pedagogical University, KorkytAta Kyzylorda State University. The experiment consisted of two stages - ascertaining and formative.

There were selected 4 groups (two control and two experimental) by the method of random selection. Two samples were drawn up $n_1 = 178$, $n_2 = 169$ students. The first group consisted of students from the control groups, and the second group - from the experimental groups.

There has been conducted the testing of knowledge in English and subject knowledge in Biology. The testing groups were put into equal conditions for the experiment. The developed methodology for the formation of students' multilingual professional competencies in the specialty “Biology”, which we used as material for the pedagogical experiment, was previously discussed with the teachers of the departments “Professional English” and “Theory and Methods of Teaching Biology”, after which there were made some adjustments to the methodology created by us.

We have also developed didactic materials for experimental teaching (preparation of lectures, seminars and laboratory classes in biological disciplines using the CLIL method,

handouts for studying special biological disciplines in English, instruction guidelines, audio and video materials on Biology in English).

For assessing the levels of students' multilingual professional competencies formation, we used diagnostic methods and methods that allow us to determine the quantitative and qualitative indicators of students according to the above criteria.

We analyzed the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment using the method of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The analysis of the results was carried out by experts who were given expert evaluation sheets. They filled in the sheets with indicated diagnostic features due to the criteria for the formation of multilingual competencies by Biology students.

The coefficient of the level of multilingual professional competencies formation of Biology students was calculated with the formula:

$$K_{\text{ПК}} = \frac{a (+2) + b (+1) + c (0) + d (-1) + e (-2)}{N},$$

where, $K_{\text{ПК}}$ - coefficient of assessment for multilingual competences formation level;

a - the number of assessments "at a high level" (+2 points);

b - the number of assessments "at a sufficient level" (+1 points);

c - the number of assessments "at the average level" (-1 points);

d - the number of assessments "at a low level" (-2 points);

e - the number of assessments "complete absence of such features" (-2 points).

N is the number of diagnostic features.

Based on the specified criteria of expert assessment, there have been determined quantitative indicators for multilingual competencies formation levels of Biology students.

Low level - from (-0.7) to (-2),

Average level - from (-0.6) to (+0.7),

Sufficient level - from (+0.8) to (+1.5).

High level - from (+1.5) to (+2).

We have determined the criterion of "proficiency in the target (English) language" using the Venn diagram methods (listening skills); monologue and dialogue on reading roles (speaking skills), scan - reading, True or false statements, essays, academic writing (writing skills).

A questionnaire was used to identify the level of students' language skills in English. The formation of students' multilingual competencies based on the results of the ascertaining and forming is presented on Table 2.

Table 2 - Formation of students' multilingual competencies based on the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment according to the criterion "proficiency in the target (English) language"

Diagnostic features	at the beginning of the experiment		at the end of the experiment	
	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)
	Listening	+0,6	+0,7	+0,7
Speaking	+0,3	+0,5	+0,5	+1,4
Reading	+0,2	+0,4	+0,3	+1,5
Writing	+0,4	+0,6	+0,5	+1,2

The data in Table 2 show that at the beginning of the experiment, students from the control and experimental groups demonstrate approximately the same level of the English language knowledge. The coefficient of assessing the level of multilingual competences formation for all diagnostic features of the development of language skills among students fluctuates within 0.2 - 0.7, which corresponds to the average level. Meanwhile, by the end of the experiment, there is an increase in the quantitative indicators of the multilingual competences formation among students of the experimental groups (within 1.2 - 1.6), which corresponds to the sufficient and high levels of formation of language skills among students of Biology.

We determined the criterion "proficiency in the content of the subject (Biology) in English" using the method of control work. Quantitative data on the formation of students' multilingual competencies based on the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Formation of students' multilingual competencies based on the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment according to the criterion "proficiency of the subject (Biology) content in English"

Diagnostic features	Coefficients of multilingual professional competencies formation			
	at the beginning of the experiment		at the end of the experiment	
	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)
knowledge of scientific biological terminology in English	+0,3	+0,4	+0,8	+1,6
understanding of academic / scientific text in English	+0,1	+0,2	+0,7	+1,5
retelling the text of educational / scientific literature	-0,2	-0,1	+0,6	+1,4
ability to compose small messages, texts	-0,2	-0,1	+0,5	+1,3
ability to answer and ask questions	-0,2	-0,3	+0,7	+1,5
the use of biological material in English in the implementation of practical tasks	-0,5	-0,7	+0,5	+1,2

We studied the criterion "proficiency in methodology of teaching Biology in English" using control tasks that require students to solve pedagogical situations (tasks) using the

methodology of content and language integrated learning. For experts, there were given samples of possible answers to each task.

The results of the expert assessment of students' competencies formation based on the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment according to the criterion "proficiency of the methodology of teaching Biology in English" are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 - Formation of students' multilingual competencies based on the results of the ascertaining and formative experiment according to the criterion "proficiency of the methodology of teaching Biology in English"

Diagnostic features	Coefficients of multilingual professional competencies formation			
	at the beginning of the experiment (ascertaining experiment)		at the end of the experiment (formative experiment)	
	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)
awareness and understanding of the essence of the CLIL method and its advantages	-0,6	-0,6	+0,1	+1,5
knowledge and operation of CLIL principles	-0,9	- 1	+0,2	+1,3
ability to plan a Biology lesson using the CLIL methodology	-0,8	-0,8	+0,4	+ 1,6
ability to teach the subject "Biology" using the CLIL methodology	1	-0,9	+0,3	+1,4
ability to organize student learning activities using CLIL methods	1	-1,1	+0,2	+1,4
ability to evaluate learning outcomes of Biology in English using CLIL methods	1,1	-1	-0,1	+1,3

We studied the criterion “development of students’ communicative competencies in the target (English) language” using speaking, eye contact, individual speaking on various topics. The quantitative data of the assessment for the formation of multilingual professional competencies of students-future biologists by the diagnostic indicators of the given criterion are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 - Formation of multilingual professional competencies of students-future biologists according to the criterion “development of students’ communicative competencies in the target (English) language”

Diagnostic features	Coefficients of multilingual professional competencies formation			
	at the beginning of the experiment (as certaining experiment)		at the end of the experiment (formative experiment)	
	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)	Control group (CG)	Experimental group (EG)
Knowledge and understanding of the communicative method of teaching English	+0,1	+0,2	+0,4	+1,5
the use of communicative methods of teaching English in Biology lesson in order to develop the language skills of students	-0,1	+0,1	+0,3	+1,3
ability to create foreign language educational and communicative environment in the lesson	-0,2	-0,3	+0,2	+1,2
the ability for effective educational dialogue and interactive action with students in Biology lesson	+0,5	+0,4	+0,7	+1,5

The results of the analysis of students’ multilingual professional competencies formation -future biologists according to the criterion “development of students’ communicative competencies in the target (English) language” show that at the beginning of the experiment, there is no significant difference in the coefficients of the formation of multilingual competencies according to this criterion among students of control and experimental groups. Meanwhile, by the end of the experiment in the experimental groups

there is a significant increase in the coefficient from “low” and “medium” levels of formation of multilingual competencies (from +0.2 to +0.7) to “sufficient” and “high” levels (from +1 , 2 to +1.5). Meanwhile, in the control groups, by the end of the experiment, there were no significant changes in the levels of formation of multilingual professional competencies among students (from -0.2 to +0.5 at the beginning of the experiment and from +0.2 to +0.7 by the end of the experiment) ...

Based on the data obtained, there have been determined levels of multilingual professional competencies formation of Biology students, which are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 - Distribution of students due to the levels of formation of multilingual professional competencies at the beginning and end of the formative experiment *

* - Note: the denominator shows the results of the ascertaining experiment, and the numerator shows the data of the forming experiment

The results of comparative analysis of the data of the ascertaining and the end of the forming experiments show the positive dynamics of multilingual professional competencies formation among Biology students in the experimental groups. If we take into account that, with the exception of experimental measures, the organization of the educational process in both samples was the same, then it can be assumed that the positive dynamics in the formation of multilingual professional competencies among students of the experimental groups was ensured by using the methodology we developed.

Conclusions and recommendations

The analysis of theoretical materials and the results of experimental work on the study of peculiarities for formation of students' professional competencies in the specialty "Biology" at higher educational institutions made it possible to draw the following conclusions and recommendations:

-training of students for the specialty "Biology" at pedagogical higher educational institutions in the context of the transition of secondary schools in Kazakhstan to the updated content of education is based on a competence-based approach, which is integrated with a multilingual approach aimed at the formation of multilingual competencies of students;

- features for the formation of students' professional competencies in the speciality "Biology" in the conditions of multilingual education are the following:

1) multilingual and multicultural competences are the important component of the expected students' learning outcomes who are capable for effective professional and pedagogical activity in a multilingual educational environment; In the context of modernization of the education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the transition of general education schools to the updated content of education, in which multilingual education is one of its important areas, the training of students in the specialty "Biology" on the basis of multilingual and multicultural educational programs seems to be especially relevant;

2) the formation of professional competence of students of the specialty "Biology" on the basis of multilingual educational programs will be based on multilingual and competence-based methodological approaches that integrate modern approaches and methods of teaching and learning with a focus on multilingual and subject competences of students;

3) in vocational and pedagogical training of students on the specialty "Biology" at the university, the educational process will be trilingual (Kazakh, Russian and English), in which, taking into account the teaching of "Biology" in secondary schools of the Republic of

Kazakhstan in English in the expected future, the volume of teaching in English will be enlarged.

4) teaching and training students on the specialty "Biology" on the basis of multilingual programs, where English is most often used as the target language, it is especially important to encourage and support the use of Kazakh or Russian languages as a tool for developing ideas and concepts by providing educational materials in the native language and training teachers to use multilingualism as a resource. It is necessary to provide opportunities for studying the content of academic disciplines, their main theories, ideas and concepts both in English and in their main (Kazakh and Russian) languages;

5) main directions of pedagogical teachers' efforts in graduating departments are:

- active cooperation, teamwork with teachers of the English language in the promotion of multilingual education of Biology students and development of language competencies of special department teachers;

- in diagnosing the level of English proficiency and subject knowledge of students in English, and on this basis the differentiated approach to the organization of educational and cognitive activities of students;

- in the use of methods to motivate students to study English and professional disciplines based on multilingual educational programs; creation of a foreign language information and educational development environment;

- in the application of the methodology of content and language integrated learning (CLIL) in teaching Biology in English;

- in the introduction of communicative methods of teaching a foreign language;

- in the education of multiculturalism among students, i.e. support of the native language and culture, uniqueness, respect for other cultures, teaching multiculturalism.

6) It is important to pay attention to the use of the developing potential of multilingual education in the formation of students' professional competencies on the specialty "Biology", to use its approaches and methods to develop academic abilities, speech skills and communicative skills of students to foster tolerance.

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